

Freshly Squeezed

Science

A reality check
on peer review

PREPRINTS IN MOTION

NEW

Peer review is a relatively new experiment

- It's only been used regularly since the 1970's
- Many prominent scientists were against the introduction of peer review
- Foundational papers in science were not themselves peer-reviewed

PREPRINTS IN MOTION

Bias is prevalent in peer review

- Gender bias
- Race bias
- Prestige bias
- Matthew effect

PREPRINTS IN MOTION

Peer reviewers do not agree with each other

- Reviewers do not agree on impact, quality, or even whether to publish or not
- One reviewer can think a study is great while another thinks it is unreliable
- 'Impact' is almost impossible to judge at the time of submission

PREPRINTS IN MOTION

Peer review does not detect fraud or gross defects

- Peer review is not designed to detect fraud
- Reviewers consistently fail to identify gross defects in studies
- By failing on these two points, peer review does not protect the literature or ensure “high-quality” publications

PREPRINTS IN MOTION

Opaque peer review hides quality control problems

- Readers do not know the history of the paper
- Problems surfaced by peer review remain hidden, unless the authors address them
- Prevents research on the peer review process
- Hinders innovation and improvements

Peer reviewers receive no formal or standard training

- Differing opinions on what peer review should achieve
- Limited awareness of the history of peer review
- Little understanding of the limitations of peer review
- No formal training in how to professionally review a paper

PREPRINTS IN MOTION

Peer reviewers receive no recognition

- Although deemed essential, institutions and journals do not reward peer review activity
- Review activity does not count for hiring or promotion
- Peer reviewers are increasingly burnt out

PREPRINTS IN MOTION

Peer review has a high cost

- Long peer review delays publication, holding back progress
- Excessive requests can damage mental health of researchers
- Requests can lead to expensive experiments, wasting funds
- Requests can delay career moves

PREPRINTS IN MOTION

Peer review mostly has a limited impact on the work

- Comparing preprints to their published versions:
 - Key conclusions in >80% don't change
 - Confidence intervals become slightly narrower
 - Research is slightly more reliable

PREPRINTS IN MOTION

Publishers themselves abuse peer review

- Nature prioritizes headline-grabbing science over robust peer review
- PNAS 'contributor' track allows authors to select their own peer reviewers
 - this leads to a vastly greater acceptance rate than normal submissions

Despite wide range of known issues, peer review acts as a stamp of approval

- Researchers, journalists and the general public treat peer-reviewed articles with less caution than non-peer reviewed work
- This leads to dangerous assumptions about trustworthiness and reliability of work

PREPRINTS IN MOTION

Peer review allows anything to eventually be published

- Mis-aligned incentives and predatory publishers enable anything to eventually be published
- This work still has the 'approval' of peer review
- Effectively diminishes the role of peer review as protecting the literature
- Damages trust in science and scientists

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PREPRINTS IN MOTION

What are the solutions?

- Transparency in peer review is vitally important
- Need dedicated rewards, recognition and career-based incentives for reviewers
- Removal of perverse incentives in publishing
- Consequences for researchers who fabricate data
- Greater transparency & speed with withdrawals and flags for problematic papers
- Adoption of multiple trust indicators and signals beyond just peer review

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